

Global Consensus on Income, Nationality Change, Inheritance Tax, Charitable and Trust Funds, and World Peace

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Abstract

Despite the Nobel Peace Prize being awarded for over a century and an increase in the number of people receiving higher education, the frequency of economic crises and wars has not decreased. One of the core factors triggering the widening wealth gap and the aforementioned issues is the unreasonable tax system. In some countries, the inheritance tax threshold is set very low, causing some individuals being unwilling or unable to inherit assets, which are then acquired by the government or corporations at low prices. High tax rates on personal income and inheritance tax lead wealthy individuals to use strategies such as emigration or various tax avoidance methods, resulting in lower tax rates compared to the middle class. This is not conducive to narrowing the wealth gap, promoting regional economic growth, alleviating their native debt crisis and reducing the economic crisis. Charitable foundations should return to their original noble purpose. Charitable or trust funds should not be used as tax-avoidance tools. Any funds or assets entering charitable foundations must be completely used for assistance purposes within a period of 3-4 years. It is recommended that governments reach a global consensus at the United Nations level regarding certain tax systems and tax avoidance issues related to charitable foundations or trust funds.

Keywords: personal income tax · personal income tax rates · inheritance tax · inheritance tax rates · gift tax · gift tax rates · nationality change tax · nationality change tax rates · tax system · tax evasion · economic growth · wealth gap · employment · regional economy · economic crisis · financial crisis · debt crisis · US treasury bonds · political behavioral economics · party behavioral economics · government behavioral economics · political party behavior economy · government behavior economy · administrative ethics · management ethics · governance · national governance · global governance · peace fighter · champion of peace · world peace · Nobel Peace Prize · governmental consensus · United Nations declaration · the UN · peace theory · methodology of peace · science communication · economic ecosystem · political ecosystem · charitable foundation · trust fund

1. An unreasonable tax system is a significant cause of widening wealth

disparity, economic or financial crises, and even wars.

Although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded every year for more than a hundred years in pursuit of Mr. Nobel's desire to maintain world peace, and despite an increasing number of university-educated students and highly educated politicians, the frequency of wars has not decreased. The power of politicians or behind-the-scenes funders who have received higher education and instigate wars is greater than that of peace fighters. Economic or financial crises are important factors that lead to wars.

Among them, there are the following main reasons: first, evil government leaders enjoy creating poverty, which is also one of the methods used to generate war populations.

Second, some countries have very low threshold points for inheritance taxation, resulting in cases where parents leaving behind legally owned properties that many descendants are unwilling to inherit, allowing the government to acquire them at a low price.

Third, wealthy individuals in populous countries often migrate to smaller countries to evade taxes. While this may be beneficial to individuals themselves, it has negative consequences for the regional economy of their home country and may increase the number of poverty-stricken individuals there. This situation is detrimental to alleviating the national debt burden.

Fourth, wealthy individuals with substantial assets are not subject to inheritance taxes, gift taxes, or immigration taxes, which hinders the regulation of regional poverty disparities.

Fifth, unreasonable inheritance and personal income tax systems not only fail to effectively regulate the wealth gap, but also lead to continuous tax avoidance measures by the wealthy. As a result, their effective tax rates are lower than those of the middle class. This leads to a continuous concentration of wealth in the hands of a very small number of individuals. Despite the increasing global money supply, there continues to be insufficient currency in circulation. This has created a distorted social psychology worldwide, where money and material possessions are considered the most important aspects of life. It perpetuates a situation where the affluent class effortlessly accumulates wealth, which is detrimental to the establishment of a global social environment based on kindness, diligence, civility, and morality. Instead, it increases the possibility of social conflict, tension, and war. For example, in April 2014, Credit Suisse Bank stated in a research report that in Russia, the top 10% wealthiest citizens control 82% of the country's total private wealth, while in the United States and China, the figures are 76% and 62% respectively. Since the 2008 financial crisis, global private wealth has been steadily increasing. In 2018, global private wealth reached \$204 trillion, a 26% increase from a decade ago. The wealth held by the richest 26 individuals is equivalent to the total wealth of the poorest 3.8 billion people (representing 50% of the global population). The top 10% hold more than 50% of the wealth, with France the lowest at 55%, followed by Russia and the United States at over 70%, and South Korea and India at over 60%. China's figure stands at 67%.

Sixth, the Matthew Effect indirectly verifies the effectiveness of the Pareto

Principle, as the poor become increasingly impoverished and the rich become even wealthier, resulting in wealth concentration in the top 20% of the population. Conversely, the Pareto Principle also validates the existence of the Matthew Effect, as the top 20% of wealthy individuals have greater opportunities to acquire resources and accumulate funds at a faster pace, leading to the perpetuation of this wealth inequality where the rich get even richer and the poor get even poorer. However, the government actions in many countries lag behind the changes in the free market, and the absence of negative feedback regulatory mechanisms means they have been unable to effectively control the Matthew Effect and the Pareto Principle in economic operations. As a result, the balancing of wealth inequality and the reduction of economic crises have not been achieved.

Specific issues of different tax systems will now be discussed, along with relevant suggestions.

2. Personal income tax rates

At present, personal income tax rates in some countries can be as high as 35-56% (1), which is excessively high and highly unreasonable. It severely lacks basic respect for individuals who legally create wealth and inevitably leads to widespread legal tax evasion by the wealthy. They can either transfer their assets to fake charitable foundations, trusts, or other means to avoid taxes. In fact, more and more people are giving up their American citizenship to avoid taxes (2). On April 13, 2022, a report released by the not-for-profit media agency ProPublica found that the real tax rate for the top 400 wealthy Americans is well below the maximum 37% tax rate set by the U.S. government (3). Economists Emmanuel Seth and Gabriel Zuckerman of the University of California, Berkeley collected U.S. tax data from 1950 and compared them (4). The results showed that in 2018, the average effective tax rate for the 400 wealthiest households in the United States was 23%, one percentage point lower than the 24.2% rate for the bottom 50% households, reflecting the irrationality of the U.S. management system. Clearly, the American system also does not encourage individuals with strong profitability to reinvest their funds back into society, thus hindering job creation and economic development in the United States. In fact, when private companies face financial crises, these individuals are forced to increase their personal investments, and some even end up losing everything. However, the national or local tax authorities do not refund the total amount of taxes paid by business owners in such cases, which is a situation that occurs frequently in China. The unreasonable national tax system is one of the reasons for the treasury bond crisis.

Taking all factors into account, it is suggested that the highest income tax rate for personal income in all countries worldwide should generally not exceed 25%. In special countries or under special circumstances, it should not exceed 30%. Investment profits in the secondary market should be included in personal income on an annual basis and taxed accordingly. Individuals who support family members or have special circumstances such as caring for parents or children's education should be granted sufficient tax deductions. Tax avoidance through false charitable funds should be prohibited. Moreover, personal income tax should not be paid twice. Any

amount already taxed through a personal company should no longer be subject to personal income tax. By reducing tax avoidance among the wealthy, the country or region will actually generate more tax revenue, alleviating the U.S. national debt crisis to some extent, and promoting consumption and investment.

3. Inheritance tax rate, nationality change tax rate and sustainable economic development and global peace

Current inheritance tax collection standards vary between countries around the world, with some countries imposing rates as high as 45-70% (5). According to statistics, in 2020 alone, there were more than 60 billion yen worth of properties in Japan that were in a state of abandonment (6). The excessively high maximum rates are highly unreasonable and show a serious lack of respect for those who have legally created wealth. When these legacies exist in the form of normally operating enterprises, excessive inheritance taxes will inevitably significantly damage the company's equity structure and bring great instability to the company's operations. This is not conducive to the effective management of the inherited enterprise by the inheritor. This inevitably leads to widespread tax evasion or the transfer of assets to fraudulent charitable foundations, disguising them as legitimate tax avoidance, or finding other ways to avoid taxes. These practices clearly hinder the rational distribution of social wealth and the proper circulation of money, and are detrimental to sustainable global peace. Therefore, reforms are necessary in the establishment and collection of global inheritance taxes.

The author believes that anyone on Earth, whether they are kings, emperors, popes, or individuals with significant assets, regardless of whether their assets belong to charitable foundations, as long as the assets are under their direct or indirect control and influence, any transfer of their own assets to charitable foundations directly or indirectly controlled by them, or to charitable foundations directly or indirectly controlled by their relatives, should still be subject to inheritance taxes based on the value of the assets. Otherwise, these charitable funds are not truly charitable funds. If they wish to inherit such assets, they must pay inheritance tax. Regardless of one's personal wealth, the maximum inheritance tax rate should not exceed 32%, and the minimum taxable threshold for wealthy individuals with varying amounts of assets should differ. Otherwise, heirs will try their best to evade taxes, leading to a widening wealth gap, intensifying social conflicts, and endless thirst or greed for wealth could potentially lead to war.

However, the author believes that regardless of individual wealth, the maximum tax rate for renouncing citizenship should not exceed 38%. Wealthy individuals with different asset levels should have different minimum tax thresholds, and individuals who renounce citizenship should have basic tax exemption guarantees. The tax rate of gift tax can be adjusted based on the model of inheritance tax.

4. Charitable or trust funds should not be used as tax-avoidance tools

Many years ago, Chinese people witnessed many Western individuals donating a large portion or their entire personal assets to charitable foundations. Everyone

believed these donors were incredibly noble. However, after a few years, it was revealed that this was not genuine philanthropy.

If a ruling party and government uphold good party ethics and government ethics, truly dedicate themselves to assisting vulnerable groups, and adhere to the principles of respecting human rights, then charitable foundations should closely adhere to their original noble purpose. Charitable or trust funds should never be used as tax avoidance tools by the wealthy, and governments around the world must promptly rectify the current chaos.

First of all, the original intention of charitable foundations is to serve society and improve the lives of the poor and marginalized. Governments should ensure that charitable funds are used for education, healthcare, relief efforts, environmental protection, and other public welfare undertakings in order to promote social fairness and justice. However, some wealthy individuals utilize charitable foundations as tax avoidance tools, transferring enormous wealth into these foundations to evade tax obligations, which go against the public interest. Governments and the United Nations should establish a governmental consensus, requiring that any funds or assets entering charitable foundations be fully and completely used for aiding vulnerable groups or specific projects within 3-4 years.

Secondly, the abuse of charitable foundations as tax avoidance tools not only damages public trust in philanthropic organizations, but also imposes an unfair burden on society. To change this situation, governments should strengthen regulatory oversight of charitable foundations to ensure the legal use of funds. In addition, governments should enhance public awareness and understanding of the charitable sector through promotion and education, encouraging wider participation.

Lastly, governments need to implement reasonable tax policies to curb the misuse of charitable foundations. On the one hand, governments should establish a sound tax framework to prevent the transfer of funds by the wealthy to foundations for the purpose of tax evasion. On the other hand, governments should provide incentives for genuine philanthropic behaviour, offering appropriate tax benefits to individuals and organizations genuinely dedicated to improving society.

To conclude, a government that upholds party ethics, government ethics, truly assists vulnerable groups, and respects human rights should promote a return to the original noble purpose of charitable foundations. The actions of governments and political parties should be evaluated using methods of metrological governmental ethics and metrological political party ethics. Charitable or trust funds must never be abused by the wealthy as tax avoidance tools. Governments worldwide must swiftly rectify the current chaos, strengthen regulatory oversight, and implement reasonable tax policies to ensure philanthropic endeavors truly achieve social equity, justice, and win-win outcomes.

5. Government consensus on global collection of income tax, renunciation tax, inheritance tax or gift tax, charitable and trust funds, and world peace

The systematic establishment and global collection of renunciation taxes and inheritance taxes can be seen as a new theory and methodology for maintaining world

peace. The author suggests that all Member States or regional organizations of the United Nations discuss and form a government consensus on the systematic establishment and global collection of inheritance taxes, and issue a government declaration on the systematic establishment and global collection of renunciation taxes and inheritance taxes or gift tax.

If the global implementation of similar tax rates for major taxes such as inheritance tax, nationality tax, and personal income tax were to be unified and agreed upon under the leadership of the United Nations, it would help prevent countries with small populations and no original wealth creation from becoming tax havens for the rich. In addition, the public in these countries would inevitably lose many job opportunities and be unable to enjoy the sustained benefits brought by economic development and increased poverty disparities, thus adding to the instability factor.

If the United Nations and global leaders, including the United States, could ensure that charitable foundations return to their original noble purpose instead of becoming de facto tax havens, it would prevent the widening wealth gap and threat to world peace caused by excessive accumulation of private wealth, which can become a catalyst for conflict and war. It is necessary to change the current situation on a global scale. If the United States takes the lead in making such changes, it will surely alleviate the severity of the national debt crisis to some extent.

If the United States, influential countries, the United Nations, and world peace organizations recognize the importance of this proposal and truly hope to build a society with universal values and sustainable peace worldwide, they should quickly consider this proposal and reach a government consensus in the short term or within a few months. The swift implementation of this consensus and the formation of new tax laws in various countries will benefit the United States and other countries in controlling its debt crisis and also enhance the sense of social responsibility of ordinary individuals who become wealthy, which will contribute to the sustainable and peaceful development of the global economic and political ecosystem.

However, if countries with high tax rates have not experienced a debt crisis, they can temporarily refrain from participating in the government's consensus actions. The suggested tax rates for inheritance tax, gift tax, and nationality change tax rates are shown in the table below (Table S 1, Table S 2.). The tax rates in the two tables are more suitable for the United States and developed countries, and can be adjusted appropriately for middle and low-income countries on this basis.

Moreover, the current inheritance tax threshold in Japan is only 30 million yen (7), which means that many ordinary citizens, even if they are impoverished or do not own any properties, are unable to inherit assets that would fulfill their basic life needs. They are forced to abandon their inheritance and allow the government to purchase it at a low price. This governmental practice evidently restricts personal freedom, violates individuals' basic right to survival, and goes against universal values. The author believes that the minimum inheritance tax threshold in Japan must be raised from the current 30 million yen to 90 million yen.

In conclusion, reforming the aforementioned tax system is beneficial for improving the economic conditions, and reducing debt and economic crisis in many

countries, narrowing the wealth gap, and promoting currency circulation. It is an important means for effectively implementing political party behavior economy and government behavior economy, and also a symbol for quantitatively testing governmental ethics. Forming a governmental consensus or United Nations declaration at the United Nations level is one of the new theories and methods to maintain lasting world peace. The United Nations should also shoulder the leadership responsibility in addressing excessive wealth disparity, while mainstream media should assume the responsibility of guiding public opinion. Individuals from all walks of life should engage in effective science communication of the aforementioned theories and methods.

Table S 1. Suggested Inherited estate or Grant tax

	Inherited estate or Grant tax	Minimum threshold	Tax rate for excess portion
1	\$20 million ≤ inherited estate < \$40 million	\$15million	between 10% and 14%
2	\$40 million ≤ inherited estate < \$60 million	\$16 million	between 10% and 14%
3	\$60 million ≤ inherited estate < \$80 million	\$17 million	between 12% and 16%
4	\$80 million ≤ inherited estate < \$100 million	\$18 million	between 12% and 18%
5	\$100 million ≤ inherited estate < \$300 million	\$20 million	between 15% and 26%
6	\$300 million ≤ inherited estate < \$500 million	\$30 million	between 20% and 28%
7	\$500 million ≤ inherited estate < \$700 million	\$40 million	between 20% and 30%
8	\$700 million ≤ inherited estate < \$900 million	\$50 million	between 20% and 30%
9	\$900 million ≤ inherited estate < \$1.2 billion	\$60 million	between 20% and 30%
10	\$1.2 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1.5 billion	\$70 million	between 22% and 30%
11	\$1.5 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1.7 billion	\$80 million	between 22% and 30%
12	\$1.7 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1.9 billion	\$90 million	between 22% and 30%
13	\$1.9 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$2.1 billion	\$100 million	between 22% and 30%
14	\$2.1 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$2.5 billion	\$110 million	between 23% and 30%
15	\$2.5 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$3 billion	\$120 million	between 23% and 30%
16	\$3 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$4 billion	\$130 million	between 23% and 30%
17	\$4 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$5 billion	\$140 million	between 24% and 30%
18	\$5 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$6 billion	\$150 million	between 24% and 30%
19	\$6 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$7 billion	\$160 million	between 25% and 30%
20	\$7 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$8 billion	\$170 million	between 25% and 30%
21	\$9 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$10 billion	\$180 million	between 26% and 30%
22	\$10 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$15 billion	\$190 million	between 26% and 30%
23	\$15 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$20 billion	\$200 million	between 26% and 30%
24	\$20 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$25 billion	\$210 million	between 27% and 32%
25	\$25 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$30 billion	\$220 million	between 27% and 32%
26	\$30 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$35 billion	\$230 million	between 28% and 32%
27	\$35 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$40 billion	\$240 million	between 28% and 32%
28	\$40 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$45 billion	\$250 million	between 28% and 32%

29	\$45 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$50 billion	\$260 million	between 28% and 32%
30	\$50 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$55 billion	\$270 million	between 28% and 32%
31	\$55 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$60 billion	\$280 million	between 28% and 32%
32	\$60 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$65 billion	\$290 million	between 28% and 32%
33	\$65 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$70 billion	\$300 million	between 28% and 32%
34	\$70 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$75 billion	\$310 million	between 30% and 32%
35	\$75 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$80 billion	\$320 million	between 30% and 32%
36	\$80 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$85 billion	\$330 million	between 30% and 32%
37	\$85 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$90 billion	\$340 million	between 30% and 32%
38	\$90 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$95 billion	\$350 million	between 30% and 32%
39	\$95 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1 trillion	\$390 million	between 30% and 32%
40	\$1 trillion ≤ inherited estate	\$370 million	between 30% and 32%

Table S 2. Suggested tax rate for nationality change

	Nationality change tax	Minimum threshold	Tax rate for excess portion
1	\$20 million ≤ inherited estate < \$40 million	\$1million	between 20% and 25%
2	\$40 million ≤ inherited estate < \$60 million	\$2 million	between 20% and 25%
3	\$60 million ≤ inherited estate < \$80 million	\$3 million	between 20% and 25%
4	\$80 million ≤ inherited estate < \$100 million	\$4million	between 20% and 25%
5	\$100 million ≤ inherited estate < \$300 million	\$5 million	between 20% and 30%
6	\$300 million ≤ inherited estate < \$500 million	\$6 million	between 20% and 30%
7	\$500 million ≤ inherited estate < \$700 million	\$7million	between 20% and 30%
8	\$700 million ≤ inherited estate < \$900 million	\$8million	between 20% and 30%
9	\$900 million ≤ inherited estate < \$1.2 billion	\$9 million	between 20% and 30%
10	\$1.2 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1.5 billion	\$10million	between 22% and 30%
11	\$1.5 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1.7 billion	\$11million	between 22% and 30%
12	\$1.7 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1.9 billion	\$12million	between 22% and 30%
13	\$1.9 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$2.1 billion	\$13million	between 22% and 30%
14	\$2.1 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$2.5 billion	\$14 million	between 25% and 32%
15	\$2.5 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$3 billion	\$15million	between 25% and 32%
16	\$3 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$4 billion	\$16 million	between 25% and 32%
17	\$4 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$5 billion	\$17 million	between 25% and 32%
18	\$5 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$6 billion	\$18million	between 25% and 32%
19	\$6 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$7 billion	\$19 million	between 25% and 32%
20	\$7 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$8 billion	\$20million	between 25% and 32%
21	\$9 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$10 billion	\$21million	between 25% and 32%
22	\$10 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$15 billion	\$22 million	between 25% and 32%
23	\$15 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$20 billion	\$23 million	between 25% and 32%
24	\$20 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$25 billion	\$24million	between 25% and 32%
25	\$25 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$30 billion	\$25 million	between 25% and 32%
26	\$30 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$35 billion	\$26 million	between 25% and 32%
27	\$35 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$40 billion	\$27 million	between 25% and 32%

28	\$40 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$45 billion	\$28 million	between 25% and 32%
29	\$45 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$50 billion	\$29 million	between 25% and 32%
30	\$50 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$55 billion	\$30 million	between 25% and 32%
31	\$55 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$60 billion	\$31 million	between 25% and 32%
32	\$60 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$65 billion	\$32 million	between 25% and 32%
33	\$65 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$70 billion	\$33 million	between 25% and 32%
34	\$70 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$75 billion	\$34 million	between 25% and 32%
35	\$75 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$80 billion	\$35 million	between 25% and 32%
36	\$80 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$85 billion	\$36 million	between 25% and 32%
37	\$85 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$90 billion	\$37 million	between 25% and 32%
38	\$90 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$95 billion	\$38 million	between 25% and 32%
39	\$95 billion ≤ inherited estate < \$1 trillion	\$39 million	between 25% and 32%
40	\$1 trillion ≤ inherited estate	\$40 million	between 32% and 38%

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